

Manifesto: Templo Ammakyn

July 29, 2025

Dr. Ammakyn (pseudonym) hereby declares the foundation of Templo Ammakyn, a temple for Angelomancy and Kabbalah, functioning in private regime since March, 2025, located in the continent of the Americas, address undisclosed to the public.

Its activities include but are not limited to: rituals, personal and/or metaphysical consultations, angelomancy kabbalit, study and development of angelic kabbalistic knowledge, teaching and mentoring. At the moment of the publication of this document, dozens of rituals and spiritual consultations have taken place over the 5 months of existence of the temple.

The textual content and identity elements used by the temple are intellectual property of Ammakyn temple's founding head, Dr. Tamit Ammakyn (pseudonym), hereby hashed, whose pseudonym is also intellectual property of its biological owner and spiritually inspired to bring Truth, Light and Love to its current and future communities:

Gematria 'Tamit Ammakyn' = 729 = תמיט עמקין = קרע שטן

Baruch HaShem

Adonai Tzevaot

Adonai Echad

Adonai Ahava